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DEFINITION OF AGRITOURISM AS A MULTIFUNCTIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN RURAL AREAS

Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani ugli

Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti

Samarqand filiali tayanch doktoranti

Email: aktamov.olimjon@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0003-8276-3799

Abstract: This paper evaluates the potential role of agritourism activities, their contribution to the sustainable rural development in Uzbekistan, considering the multifunctional development of rural areas. The paper also analyses the long dating Polish experience on the farm rural tourism activities and the rural development policy providing incentives to the diversification of farming activities. The lessons learnt from the Poland case analysis provide some suggestion for the rural development policy design in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: agritourism, deconstructing agritourism definitions, Discrepancy of agritourism definitions, elements of multifunctional development, transformations in agriculture and rural areas, agritourism as an economic development tool.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda qishloq hududlarini barqaror rivojlantirishda agroturizm faoliyatining roli va uning ko'p funktsiyali rivojlanishga qo'shgan hissasi baholanadi. Shuningdek, unda Polshaning uzoq yillik fermerlik asosidagi qishloq turizmi tajribasi va qishloq xo'jaligida diversifikatsiyani rag'batlantiruvchi siyosat tahlil qilinadi. Polsha tajribasining tahlili O'zbekistonda qishloq rivojlanish siyosatini shakllantirish uchun foydali tavsiyalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: agriturizm, agriturizm ta'riflarini tahlil qilish, agriturizm tushunchasidagi tafovutlar, ko'p funktsiyali rivojlanish elementlari, qishloq xo'jaligi va qishloq hududlaridagi o'zgarishlar, agriturizm iqtisodiy rivojlanish vositasi sifatida.

Аннотация: В данной статье оценивается потенциальная роль агротуристической деятельности и её вклад в устойчивое развитие сельских территорий Узбекистана с учётом многофункционального подхода. Также проводится анализ многолетнего польского опыта в сфере сельского туризма на базе фермерских хозяйств и государственной политики, направленной на стимулирование диверсификации сельскохозяйственной деятельности. Изучение польского опыта позволяет предложить определённые рекомендации для разработки эффективной политики развития села в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: агротуризм, анализ определений агротуризма, расхождения в определениях агротуризма, элементы многофункционального развития, трансформации в сельском хозяйстве и на селе, агротуризм как инструмент экономического развития.

INTRODUCTION

Agritourism has been increasingly offered to the consumers in many different parts of the world, including in Uzbekistan, since it is not only providing economic returns, but also able to conserve natural resources.

Although the perceptions of agritourism might vary among regions and countries, key element of agritourism activities is the involvement of visitors in related agricultural activities. To maintain the benefits of agritourism, understanding of the concepts of agritourism managements and establishing sustainable agritourism one country needs highly effective measures and innovative ideas to rely upon and follow though the exact structure, but in order to reach that particular expected outcome and spread it in different part of its region, there has to be scrutinized research analysis and deep learned approach.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

According to National Geographics Dictionary (2020), rural area is an open swath of land that has few homes or other buildings, and not very crowded people.¹ The Classification of areas are called as rural if they fall outside of settlements with more than 10,000 resident population. Prior to explaining other meanings of related terms, let's look at the definition of rural area in global context. For instance, Canadian Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development states that rural region of the country is called rural area, if density of the population becomes less than 400 people per square kilometer (Statistics Canada 2007)² In USA 84% of the population resides in suburban areas. Cities only remain 10% of the country, but remaining 90% amounts to residents live in rural areas. United States Census Bureau identifies population density and defines percentage of rural areas. The area with no more than 2,500 residents is called rural (U.S Census Bureau)³. Rural and agri-tourism may offer almost unlimited number of products and services. Agri-tourism farms and rural tourism small enterprises may be successful where varied and attractive enough portfolio is offered. An analysis of recent rural and agri-tourism products reveals that some of them are rural or agriculturally related and the others are "artificial" and do not belong to rural areas. As a result there is a necessity to arrange and structure rural and agri-tourism services, products and imponderables (Sznajder, M., & Przezbórska, L., 2004)⁴.

Whereas National Official Register of the Territorial Division of Poland analyses the rural area basing on the Poland regional location and describes it as follows it analyses the diversity and the degree of economic development and standard of living in rural areas in Poland with regard to: demographic and social features, economic situation of the population, residential conditions, technical and social infrastructure, use of lands, the production features of agriculture, natural environment, and also the sources of financing rural areas. And saying it in numbers, rural areas covered 93% country's area and were inhabited by almost 40% population of Poland in 2018 (Statistics Poland 2019).⁵ In Uzbekistan, total usable agricultural area consists of 62% of the whole area. Taking into account the given size of fertile land, each regions of Uzbekistan owns this accordingly. It should be emphasized that ratio between the numbers of urban and rural population remains almost equal, 51% to 49%, respectively (Republic of Uzbekistan State Statistics Committee, 2019)⁶. Our main goal also consists of identifying agriculturally usable lands across both countries to use them in various initiatives by applying multifunctional development measures and it is also noteworthy that we are going to accomplish it in rural areas. Well, purposes of rural development are the provision of stable social and economic growth, increased agricultural production, an empowered agricultural efficiency, full employment of the rural population, raising the standard of living, and rational use of land.

In addition to economic benefits, tourism provides the host countries with wide-scope of cultural developments, in other words, tourism tempts many people who comes from different cultural background to visit the country, to spend time, learn local tradition in there, what is more, it creates friendly atmosphere across the countries, and boosts many other tourists discover the new areas and people in turn. Let's briefly get to be familiarized with the word "rural tourism" in short. As thoroughly explained in literature review, rural tourism conception faces some uncertainty because of its wide-interrelation to different fields of industries and activities, nonetheless, some narrowed focus area has been given. For instance, even, a holiday can be as rural tourism, but the following characteristics should be contained in the holiday. It should (Figure 1):

1 National Geographic Dictionary(2020). "Rural Area" <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/encyclopedia/rural-area/> - accessed on 28 February 2021

2 Statistics Canada 2019. "Rural area" <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/n1/pub/92-195-x/2011001/geo/ra-rr/ra-rr-eng.htm> - accessed 20 February 2021

3 U.S Census Bureau <https://www.census.gov/library/stories/2017/08/rural-america.html#:~:text=Urban%20areas%20make%20up%20only,of%20the%20population%20lives%20there.> – accessed 28 February 2021.

4 MICHAŁ SZNAJDER, LUCYNA PRZEBÓRSKA. Identification of rural and agri-tourism products and services. 2004

5 Statistics Poland 2016, "Obszary wiejskie w Polsce w 2016 r. Rural areas in Poland in 2016" p 25. <https://stat.gov.pl/en/topics/agriculture-forestry/agriculture/rural-areas-in-poland-in-2016,3,3.html> – accessed on 1 March 2021.

6 <https://api.stat.uz/api/v1.0/data/hududlar-boyicha-shahar-va-qishloq-aholisi-soni?lang=en&format=pdf>

Figure 1. Core Characteristics of Agritourism in the Context of Rural Development

Coming to agritourism, it is closely related with farmers' markets where farm products and agricultural production take place to be sold (Wicks & Merrett, 2003)⁷. Other than that, according to C. Barbieri (2010)⁸, agritourism particularly includes hospitality services (e.g., lodging, food services, event programming) where, as part of its service, this service offers recreational activities in rural areas. Tourists and visitors may enjoy the joyful outdoor activities, and this is first. Secondly, considering many visitors coming from urban society, these programs give them the great chance to get back to nature, they can be informed with local farms and farm products in remote part of the countries where full of fresh air, especially the beauty of the nature is amazing. Third of all, this kind of services gives visitors opportunity to participate directly into the ongoing farming process and observe them. (Barbieri, 2010)

Agritourism is not a recent phenomenon; furthermore, it has considerably increased in the past ten years and is projected to continue growing in the future. Despite such growth, there is not a shared understanding of agritourism which is problematic as this creates confusion and lessens its appeal among consumers, further hindering communication and collaboration among stakeholders. Therefore, a study on perception of farmers in agri-tourism in Tamilnadu (capital city is Chennai, Southern India) was conducted in 2011 to identify preferred definitional elements and types of agritourism activities across residents, farmers, and extension faculty in Missouri and North Carolina (U.S.). Results showed that "agricultural setting", "entertainment", "farm", and "education" should be included in a good definition of agritourism. Respondents also agreed that agritourism includes staged or authentic activities carried out on working agricultural facilities. All stakeholder groups rejected to consider activities offered in non-working farms or where the agricultural setting only serves for background purposes as agritourism. Statistical tests showed significant differences on agritourism definitional elements and types across groups, results that are further discussed. Besides advancing the understanding of the meaning of agritourism, this study carries important implications for the practice of agritourism (K. Rajesh, 2016)⁹.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology involves qualitative content analysis of academic literature, policy documents, and international case studies related to agritourism. Data were collected through document review and expert opinion surveys. The analysis focused on identifying key components of multifunctional rural development and comparing definitional approaches across different contexts.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Definitions of agritourism are abundant in the literature, reflecting the ambiguity surrounding its meaning. (Arroyo, Barbieri, 2013)¹⁰. Now, the word "multifunctional" itself means having many functions of something. If we interpret it into application, multifunctional rural development refers to rural part of a country to be socio-economically broad in many functions. Let's see by elements of multifunctional rural development: they are:

7 Bruce E. Wicks and Christopher D. Merrett. Agritourism: An Economic Opportunity for Illinois. 2003

8 Carla Barbieri. An Importance-Performance Analysis Of the Motivations Behind Agritourism and Other Farm Enterprise Developments in Canada. 2010

9 K.Rajesh. A Study on Perception of Farmers In Agri-Tourism in Tamilnadu. 2016

10 Claudia Gil Arroyo, Carla Barbieri, Samantha Rozier Rich. Defining agritourism: A comparative study of stakeholders' perceptions in Missouri and North Carolina. 2013

Agricultural production activities (which contains farm activities, growing of crops etc.)
 Non-agricultural activities (which closely related with supplying production services and materials),
 Non-farming activities (Rural tourism, agritourism, Forest economy, Landscape care and environment protection).

Among these three, Non-farming sub-elements play significantly major role in the development of the rural economy. Because it supports tourism function in rural areas and agricultural industry (Ayazlar & Ayazlar, 2015)¹¹ (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Key Dimensions in Defining Agritourism: Conceptual Challenges and Interpretive Factors

A major discrepancy of agritourism definitions relate to the type of setting where the activity occurs. Most studies state that agritourism must be carried out on a farm (Carpio, 2008.). While fewer expand the setting to any type of agricultural setting, such as farms, ranches, nurseries, and others (Abbey, 2018.)¹²

Furthermore, in their studies Wicks & Merrett (2003), "Rural Research Report" have even included some types of off-farm facilities, such as farmers' markets, where produce and other farm products are taken away from the agricultural production setting to be sold (Katsoni & Dionysopoulou 2015)¹³. Inconsistencies in the type of setting may be due to the different meanings used to define agricultural establishments, especially related to "farm". Thus, comprising ranches, nurseries, among similar establishments. Meanwhile, the E.U. defines a farm as an agricultural holding, meaning "economic unit under a single management engaged in agricultural production activities" and which can also engage in non-agricultural activities (OECD, 1999, p.5). Thus, following definitions allow for a broad interpretation of what an agricultural facility contains. At this point, it is worth mentioning that "rurality" as the agritourism setting is no longer a debatable argument since academic developments in the last decade have advanced to clearly separate "agritourism" from "rural tourism" (Arroyo, Barbieri 2013). A second commonly found disagreement surrounds the authenticity paradigm related to the agricultural facility and to the experience offered. As for the authenticity of the facility, for instance, based on Weaver and Fennell's (2015) definition in Tourism Management which explicitly excludes activities and experiences that are developed in non-working farms because they deem necessary the commercial aspect involved in this activity (Katsoni & Dionysopoulou 2015).

A third definitional disagreement relates to the activities that agritourism comprises which is not surprising given the extent of inconsistencies related to its meaning. Such inconsistencies may be geo-political as they seem to be associated to government policies. For example, according to Sonnino R. in her "Sociologia Ruralis", she included hospitality related services (e.g., lodging) when examining agritourism in Southern Tuscany (Italy) which is consistent with its inclusion in the Italian National Legal Framework for Agritourism granted in 1985. (Katsoni & Dionysopoulou 2015).

Barbieri (2012), states that in North America hospitality services (e.g., lodging, food services, event programming) as part of the agritourism offer arguing strong synergies with the offer of recreational activities. Similar discrepancies also exist related to educational activities and agritourism (Tew, C., & Barbieri, C., 2012). Finally, an ontological discussion surrounding the definition of agritourism could be added to the preceding debate in relation to the need of "travel", especially because the term "tourism" is embedded in the label most commonly used in the literature to depict this activity (agritourism) (Katsoni & Dionysopoulou 2015). The World

11 Gökhan Ayazlar & Reyhan A. Ayazlar. Rural Tourism: A Conceptual Approach. 2015

12 Abbey Fluckiger. What are the determinants, economic and socio-economic outcomes of agritourism in the U.S. 2018

13 Vicky Katsoni, Panagiota Dionysopoulou. Agritourism Marketing Distribution Strategy And Typology Investigation. The Case Of Arcadia. 2015

Tourism Organization defines tourism as “the activities of persons traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes not related to the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited” (OECD, 2001.p1.1), thus suggesting some sort of travel. However, none of the agritourism definitions reviewed refers to the need of travel, which can be related to the lack of affirm understanding of what travel entails, ranging from minimum distances such as the standard 50-mile one-way used in the U.S. to the minimum of one overnight stay used in many other countries (C. G. Arroyo, C. Barbieri [2013](#)).

There is a great deal of interest in agritourism as a niche tourism sector for farms. People are looking for an authentic farm experience that might link them to their past or that teaches them something new. Visitors also want relief from the stress of everyday life to experience a seemingly simpler life. Farm visits offer a day in the country, where guests may pick berries, go for a hayride, sample homegrown or homemade products, see animals, and learn how farms operate. The variety of agritourism experiences that can be offered is huge - from farm lodging or farm-based recreation such as hiking or hunting, to pumpkin patches, u-pick farms, farm festivals, wine tasting, farm restaurants, agri-entertainment like corn mazes and more. Visitors are willing to pay for these experiences as long as the price is reasonable and they find value in what is being offered (M. Roth and J. Ochtersk, [2016](#))¹⁴. In line with such inconsistencies, some agritourism definitions may imply some sort of travel when mainly referring to farm-stays or entailing any type of accommodations, while other studies suggest that agritourism usually entails one-day visits in local communities.

Multifunctional rural development is a very broad term, which is variously interpreted. It is commonly considered to be rural activation and diversification of business activity so that the future of rural people is connected not only with agriculture but also with the branches of the economy that are alternative to agriculture (Sznajder, [2009](#), p.45)¹⁵. It is particularly concerned with creating new opportunities for employment and overcoming unemployment, searching for alternative sources of income in professions related to the agricultural environment and the diversification of profit-generating activities using rural resources.

The strategy of multidirectional rural development consists in diversification of the rural economy, thus abandoning mono-functionality, which usually involves the production of agricultural commodities or raw materials. Multifunctional development involves introducing an increasing number of new non-agricultural functions – production, trade and services – into rural space. Thus, the country ceases to be an area inhabited by traditional farmers where only farming materials are produced, but becomes an integrated part of national economy, a place inhabited by people related to both agriculture and non-agricultural branches of life (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Classification of Economic Activities in Relation to Agriculture and Agritourism

The processes of multifunctional rural development may run in two directions: as an external inflow of ideas, capital, conceptions and organizational solutions and as the development of local enterprise and economic activity of the community of rural inhabitants. In addition, multifunctional rural development highly relies on space conditions, including the following:

Demographic factors (e.g. population and its structure, density, migration, dual professions, unemployment,

14 Jim Ochterski Monika Roth. Getting started in agritourism. 2016

15 Michal Sznajder, Lucyna Przezbórska, Frank Scrimgeour. Agritourism. 2009.

qualification and education, etc.);

Natural (earth resources, soil quality, climate, terrain sculpture, forest density, scenic values, etc.)

Capital;

Infrastructure (mainly technical and social infrastructure);

Others (especially those related with the state's regional policy, region location, agrarian and property structure (Sznajder, [2009](#), p.35)

The factors conditioning rural development itself can be divided into two groups: endogenous and exogenous factors. The endogenous conditions include work resources, rural production potential, technical infrastructure of rural areas and know-how level. Whereas, the exogenous factors, i.e., those affecting rural development, include the macroeconomic efficiency of the national economy and agriculture (Sznajder, [2009](#), p.48). Multifunctional development depends on economic conditions, which include farming effectiveness, work efficiently, production increase, improvement in the area structure of farms, creating new employment opportunities in small towns and villages (including non-farming employment), counteracting people's migration to cities and depopulation of regions, new forms of economic activity.

In Europe the first serious proposal to develop rural areas appeared along with the establishment of the European Economic Community, through a uniform concept of rural development policy originated only in the mid-1980s. For the purpose of supporting the European rural world, the two major EU policies have converged: agrarian and regional, meaning that the Rural Development policy in the EU has been navigating between both waters, that of sectorial policy and territorial policy. Thus, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) has tried to link the policy of agricultural structures with development aspects up to the 1988 reform of Structural Funds, while the Regional Policy, in addition to integrating the European Agricultural Guidance (University Cordoba, Spain 2010)– guidance, has been articulating a Community Initiative on Rural Development (2009) with its same structural funds (Rural Development policy of the European Union 2010) (Rosa Gallardo-Cobos, [2010](#)).

In Poland, Rural Development is managed nationally through one Rural Development Programme (RDP), funded under the [European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development \(EAFRD\)](#) and national contributions. The RDP sets out priority approaches and actions to meet the needs of the specific geographical area it covers. Rural development funding through the EAFRD is part of a broader framework of [European Structural and Investment Funds \(ESI Funds\)](#), including also Regional Development, Social, Cohesion, and Fisheries Funds. These are managed nationally, by each EU Member State, on the basis of Partnership Agreements, strategic plans outlining the country's goals and investment priorities (European Commission ENRD Poland, [2021](#)).

In Uzbekistan the same measures, listed below, are held and organized by JICA (Japan International Cooperation Agency). The economy of Uzbekistan is driven by the export of natural resources such as natural gas and gold, and it has maintained a high level of economic growth for a number of years. In order to continue that high economic growth, however, it is necessary to improve a climate for business and investment, modernize agriculture, renovate and improve economic infrastructure and take other steps. Japan's Country Assistance Policy for Uzbekistan of April 2012 lists three areas of focus: 1) economic infrastructure renovation and improvement (transport and energy), 2) providing support for human resource development and institutional building to facilitate the transition to a market economy along with promoting the economy and industry, and 3) support for restructuring the social sector (Agriculture and rural development and Healthcare). Based on this, JICA provides cooperation for power generation and railroad projects, for human resource development in local businesses through the Uzbekistan-Japan Center For Human Development, for improvement in the legal infrastructure for business activities, and for agriculture and health care (JICA, [2020](#)).

Transformations in Agriculture and Rural Areas

While definitions vary, rural transformation is recognized as a process impacting on development with or without interventions. In other words, it constitutes the dynamics in the rural space and does not by itself provide directions for sustainable development. Julio Berdegué states that rural transformation can be defined as a process of comprehensive societal change whereby rural societies diversify their economies and reduce their reliance on agriculture; become dependent on distant places to trade and to acquire goods, services, and ideas; move from dispersed villages to towns and small and medium cities; and become culturally more similar to large urban agglomerations. All over the world, the transformation processes affect the lives of about 4.6 billion people who work 60 per cent of the world's arable land and produce almost two thirds of food and non-food agricultural products. Rural transformation poses great challenges to rural people and areas, but also it provides great opportunities for sustainable development. Recognizing these challenges as well as exploiting the opportunities can decide whether a society lives through a "brutal" or "benign" transformation (Berdegué, [2014](#))¹⁶.

Policy for benign agricultural transitions If agrarian transitions are to be gentle, where people voluntarily

16 <https://www.donorplatform.org/challenges-and-opportunities-of-rural-transformation.html>

leave farming for better prospects rather than being forced off their land, then three things have to be in place. First, smallholders who specialize in farming need to be able to raise production and productivity. They have to be able to obtain better inputs, technical knowledge, financial services and information about markets. Rural markets do not typically work well for smallholders in providing inputs and finance. Hence finding the institutional innovations that will overcome the failings of rural markets becomes a priority for agricultural (and rural) development. Second, land markets need to function for efficiency and equity. At issue are small-scale transfers of land between those smallholders specializing in farming and those who do not, being unable or unwilling to cultivate all their land. Such transfers are often likely to be of use rights rather than outright sale – through loans, share-cropping and rentals. Tenure policy needs to facilitate these exchanges by arrangements that give both parties confidence in the deal agreed, with legal recognition of the exchange. At the same time, the land rights of disadvantaged land users who may lose their land need to be recognized. More will be said about land policy later in this section. Three, rural people need to be in condition to take up non-farm jobs. That means provision of schooling, healthcare and clean water so that young adults have the capabilities to take up jobs off the land, albeit perhaps with additional training for which schooling is a precondition (GIZ agricultural policy 2015, P.38).

The land affecting the environment and landscape as well as provides momentum for rural transformation, even though technical progress has considerably reduced the demand for agricultural labor, thus also reducing the economic importance of agriculture. In the most developed countries, both the proportion of agricultural labor and the share of agriculture in macroeconomic indicators (mainly including GDP) is only a few percent. In the case of Poland, this mostly means the positive aspects of the transformation that followed the fall of real socialism and the accession to the EU. the radical economic reform in early 1990s, the formation of development support institutions, and the high education levels of a large part of the society (inherited from the socialist era). Also, natural and cultural values that condition the development of natural tourism, including agritourism which represents an additional activity of farms, have also mattered in the last decades were the factors that indicate the transformation (Sadowski, A., Wojcieszak-Zbierska, M.M. & Beba, P.,[2021](#))¹⁷.

Agritourism as an economic development tool

Economic benefits for farm households are not homogeneous across all farms or operators, with reports of agritourism's economic impacts varying between studies, though all reports show at least some economic benefit. Barbieri and Tew's (2016) study of Missouri agritourism which was a research project between the Missouri Department of Agriculture (MDA) and the University of Missouri Department of Parks, Recreation and Tourism (MU-PRT). This sampling strategy resulted in a total of 592 farms. It reported that the highest increase in profits due to agritourism participation, with half of participants reporting 50% increases in earnings and an additional quarter of participants reporting earnings increases of over 100%. The figures are likely unrealistically high due to selection bias and the exclusion of non-working agritourism farms (Barbieri and Tew, [2016](#). p.34). Conversely, McGehee and Kim (2004) report the smallest economic impact, an average total revenue increase of just 5%; however, even minimal revenue increases may provide enough income to prevent farm bankruptcy (Mc. Gehee 2007. P 280-289).

Schilling et al. (2014) conducted the most reliable study ascertaining economic impacts of agritourism on farm profits, comparing net cash incomes between similar farms participating and not participating in agritourism diversification (Abbey, [2018](#), p.13). The results are as follows (Figure 4):

Figure 4. Impact of Agritourism on Farm Profitability by Farm Size and Farmer Type

17 Arkadiusz Sadowski, Monika Małgorzata Wojcieszak-Zbierska, Patrycja Beba. Territorial differences in agricultural investments co-financed by the European Union in Poland. 2021

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